

The Concept of Feminism to Liberation in Atwood's the Edible Woman

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Abstract

*Margaret Atwood, the Canadian feminist writer is concerned with the issues and the problems of the Canadian women. By addressing the concerns of the Canadian women folk, she represents the socio-cultural, economic and political back-drop of the Canadian women. Feminism is the condition in which an individual gets an opportunity to act according to his or her own will. This feminism to liberty is restricted to women in a male dominated society. It is believed that a woman is subordinate to man. Atwood portrays her protagonists as women thriving to achieve freedom and emancipation. Atwood, with a wide Canadian cultural canvas, depicts the essentials of woman's sense of individuality in her novels. She has to initially overcome the physiological hurdle as being a woman, and then establishes herself as an individual. Atwood depicts Marian in *The Edible Woman* as a liberated woman releasing herself from the clutches of marriage. In this novel Marian, protagonist liberates herself from the women related problems and begin to subscribe to a style of living where she is ample space for individual's desires and ultimately, for absolute freedom. However, one should remember that the protagonist willingly position herself within the framework of her east and west society.*

Keywords: feminist, liberty, liberation, liberated, bondage, postcolonial, etc.,

Margaret Atwood, the Canadian feminist writer is concerned with the issues and the problems of the Canadian women. By addressing the concerns of the Canadian women folk, she represents the socio-cultural, economic and political back-drop of the Canadian women. Atwood, as Commonwealth writer focuses her attention on postcolonial issues related to women and thereby attempt to bring out the struggles of the suppressed and marginalized women in Canada. Her unique combination of latent energy and personal history equips her to join the ongoing political discourse in order to interpret this cultural moment to a growing audience. Her texts question social, political, and literary ideas, beliefs, and conventions as they delight, inform, intrigue, and sometimes, irritate the readers. Her first novel, *The Edible Woman* (1969) is about a woman who cannot eat and feels that she is being eaten.

Feminism is the condition in which an individual gets an opportunity to act according to his or her own will. This feminism to liberty is restricted to women in a male dominated society. It is believed that a woman is subordinate to man. She revolts against the

existing social order and tries to create a new order of life. At times, she subverts the codes of the conventional society in order to withdraw from a state of restraints and compulsions. In the existing social structure a woman faces discriminations for being a girl, a wife, a mother and also a woman, and these drive her to choose a free path of her own choice, a path of revolt and resistance. This attitude of resistance is a recurring theme in most women's writings. Much of women's writing can be seen not as an attempt to define an isolated individual ego but as a venture to discover a collective concept of subjectivity which foregrounds the motif of identity in relationship.

Atwood portrays her protagonists as women thriving to achieve freedom and emancipation. Atwood, with a wide Canadian cultural canvas, depicts the essentials of woman's sense of individuality in her novels. In a conservative society a woman is taught to be shy, gentle and dignified as a person, pure and faithful as a wife, and selfless, loving and thoughtful as a mother. The male-dominated society has imposed certain traditional norms on women, thus restricting them from going beyond stereotyped roles. These roles prevent them to think individually and act independently. Whenever they attempt to cross the barriers they face many hurdles both physically and psychologically. Many of them resist the conventional social order and choose to lead a life of their own, thereby becoming indifferent to their society. Gender-discrimination, in any society, is a stumbling block to a woman who wants to be successful. She has to initially overcome the physiological hurdle as being a woman, and then establishes herself as an individual. Atwood depicts Marian in *The Edible Woman* as a liberated woman releasing herself from the clutches of marriage.

Marian suffers to a very great extent while they try to resist or deviate from the existing social environment. Atwood makes her heroines experience the taste of freedom while they concretize her desire for individuality and freedom. In the Canadian soil, enforcement of individualism in one's life is perhaps possible. Marian, a young woman, rebels against her forthcoming marriage. She finds her fiancé Peter as too ordinary for he finds the role of wife as simply conventional. Brought up amidst Canadian moralistic values, Marian believes in liberal social values. She shares her room with Ainsley who contradicts her in all familial issues. Both go to the house of Clara, Marian's colleague. Clara's husband Joe helps her in bringing up the children. Clara is pregnant for the third time. Ainsley, who is against the concept of marriage, finds fault with Clara. But Marian thinks that Joe and Clara are placed in an ideal situation for rearing children. But, for Ainsley the father-image of Joe and the mother-image of Clara are confusing. She says, "The thing that ruins families these days is the husbands. Have you noticed she isn't even breast – feeding the baby?" (40). On seeing Clara's children, Marian develops a liking towards making a home of her own with Peter her lover, whereas Ainsley who does not believe in marriage wants to beget a baby outside the premises of marriage.

By projecting these two polarized characters Atwood highlights the feminist dimension of liberty and individuality. In this novel, *The Edible Woman* Marian, at the beginning, likes to get married to Peter, a conventional young lawyer. Later, she decides to run away from the system of marriage. Her quest for normalcy makes her violate all conventions. Marian considers herself a victim while Peter and Ainsley pursue their prey. By refusing to marry, she liberates herself from social expectations and also from incompatible marriage. Marian accepts Duncan probably for the reason that he will allow her to continue to remain herself. In exercising her desire to remain an individual she unfolds a new path in her life. Her individuality makes her remain single and destroy the cultural links between the external world and her inner self. Ainsley has no faith in marriage. She declares, "I'm not going to get married. That's what's wrong with most children, they have too many parents" (40). But she believes in giving birth to children. She wants every woman to have at least one child. Marian, on hearing this, gets shocked and tries to prevent her from going for an

illegitimate child. These two basically opposed women characters operate differently in the process of resisting conventions. Marian resists the existing system. She thinks she has every right to live with a man of her choice. But she likes to be free from bondage, as she does not want to be a victim in the system of marriage. On the other hand, Ainsley who dislikes marriage intends to give birth to a son. But after giving birth to a son she goes in search of a father and chooses Fischer as her husband. While Marian advises her not to do so in the interest of her child, Ainsley responds that if she does not show a father to her son, he would become a homosexual.

Marian represents Seymour Surveys, a market research company that is collecting details to improve the quality of beer. This profession gives her ample opportunities to meet different types of men. It is here that she meets Fischer, Duncan and Trevor who live in one room. She is very much impressed by Duncan's behaviour. All her questions are answered by Duncan philosophically; to Duncan's one question as to why she chooses this job Marian quietly answers that she has to survive and that she holds only a B.A degree. Clara, wife and mother of two children, says that she was attracted towards Joe only for his ordinariness that has raised him to perfection. On the other hand, Marian and Peter give importance only to face values: We had been taking each other at our face values, which meant we had got on very well. Of course I had to adjust to his moods, but that's true of any man, and his were too obvious to cause much difficulty. (61) Peter wants Marian to cook, but she deliberately avoids cooking for the reason that her cooking would be a threat to him. She even curbs her wit while commenting on Peter. She checks her height to see whether it suits Peter's. Though she wants to contradict some of his views, she checks herself as she does not want to spoil her marriage with him. She changes herself in such a way that she becomes a suitable companion to Peter.

Marian thinks that Peter feels jealous whenever she talks to some one. But when Peter talks to Len and other friends along with Ainsley, Marian expects him to pay heed to her. When Peter ignores her she starts crying and runs into the Ladies Powder Room to hide her tears. She admits that she wants Peter to run after her: "I must have been expecting Peter to chase me..." (72). Len, a television man, and also a friend to Marian, becomes Peter's good friend. Marian and Peter quarrel over their right to be the first friend to Len. Marian feels happy when Peter is in search of her. She also realizes that Peter and she herself deliberately avoid talking about their future because they know that there is no such thing. At this juncture, Ainsley warns Marian that Peter is monopolizing her. Gradually, Marian musters her strength to ascertain her self. She says, "I would have to decide what I wanted to do" (77). After the incident in the Powder Room and her flight from the party Marian reveals her state of evasiveness. She develops a mental conflict about establishing a career and maintaining her love affair with Peter. Marian turns out to be a typical twentieth century woman facing the contradicting and divisive tendencies of the society. Her profession requires her to manipulate words as she has to read the minds of people and render them into words. As Marian does not have a home or mother she automatically takes her room-mate and colleagues as her role models. In this way, Ainsley strikes Marian as one with a different life style. At Marian's office, her friends who are her elders encourage her to get married. She knows that Ainsley and Clara give importance to child-bearing. She finds in Clara an ant queen and an egg producer. She is aware that Ainsley likes to give birth to a child without getting married. Marian is totally confused.

Throughout the novel, Atwood discusses the problem of procreation that makes society look down upon women. Marian describes the office structure as an ice – cream sandwich with the male executives at the top, the mechanical equipment at the bottom, and her department in the middle. In the words of Raren F. Stein, "The culinary description of her office echoes the motif initiated in the book's title. And at the crux of the food imagery lies the heroine's awareness that women in contemporary western society are perceived as consumable commodities. (46) Marian's running

out from the friends' meeting and her hiding under Len's bed imply that she tries to create a sense of awareness in Peter about herself and Len. Her actions and quarrels with Peter make him ask, "How do you think we'd get on as... how do you think we'd be, married?" (83). Ainsley comes to know that Peter and Marian are engaged. Without showing any interest, she tells Marian, "Well, if I were you I'd get married in the states, it'll be so much easier to get a divorce when you need one. I mean, you don't really know him, do you?" (84). Marian ascertains herself and discloses to Ainsley that she is going to marry Peter. But Ainsley is in search of a good breed who can father her child. Marian goes to Clara's house along with Ainsley; there she happens to see Clara's sufferings with two children and a third one in her womb. Since this time Marian takes care of the domestic work with all care and commitment. Simultaneously, Ainsley who closely absorbs every thing slips away from the principle of remaining single and getting into the system of marriage. Marian argues in favour of marriage and the need for adjustment in life. While Clara speaks to Ainsley, she admits that she has lost her identity as an individual due to her marriage. "She had read a French novel and a book about archaeological expeditions in Peru and talked about night school. Lately, she had taken to making bitter remarks about being, 'just a housewife'" (38).

Marian hesitates to get into wedlock as she closely watches the suffering of her friend Clara with her children. At Clara's residence, the discussion about breast-feeding makes Marian think more about marriage and she foresees the dangers in the system of marriage. She intends to free herself from the bondage of contingency and to carve for herself an identity not dependent on marriage or man. Though women's career is understood as a promoter of their identity, Marian's job as a consumer consultant for Seymour Surveys does not help her in any way in elating her identity. While she goes for her survey she meets Duncan and Fisher with whom she develops friendship. To Marian, her work is not satisfying in nature; it seems dead by nature. Even her office women, most of them are elders to her, are eager to listen to Marian about Peter and their marriage.

On the other hand, Atwood's Marian decides to escape from the bondage of marriage before falling into the traps of Peter. Her professional skill as a market researcher helps her to assess Peter and his attitude towards life. To Peter, marriage is a tool to subdue women. As a typical representative of the patriarchal set-up he spells out his idea of marriage: "you can't continue to run around indefinitely; people who are not married get funny in middle age, embittered or addled or something; I've seen enough of them around the office to realize that" (102). But Marian sincerely wants to marry Peter and make a home of her own. She likes to continue her job for a while longer to make money. "We'll probably have to live in an apartment at first, but later we can have a real house, a permanent place; it will be worth the trouble to keep clean" (102).

Marian wants to write a letter to her home about her marriage which may please her parents. Peter never speaks about his parents to Marian. It is on this line of logic he moves out and buys a book on marriage. At the beginning, despite the warnings given by Ainsley, Joe and Clara, she thinks of man and marriage as means to selfhood. Though she is defined and limited by Peter she does not object to his habit of making her whatever he wants her to be. To him, she is "the kind of girl who wouldn't try to take over his life" (61). She also admits, "Of course I had to adjust to his moods, but that's true of any man, and his were too obvious to cause much difficulty" (61).

In Atwood's *The Edible Woman*, after her accidental meeting with Duncan at the Laundromat, Marian observes, "We stood facing each other are absolutely. As though someone had pulled a switch, we dropped our laundry bags... Found myself kissing him" (100). Marian's friendship with Duncan and Fischer at the Laundromat enables her to escape from Peter's conspiracy which was to enslave her in the name of marriage. Duncan, who acts as a shrewd psychologist, is perfectly aware of the impression he makes and uses it to play on Marian's last illusions, illusions that her pride is her own sexual competence and her concept of herself is the 'Nurse bringing the Gift of life'. He

persuades her to bed, with his concocted tale that he is a virgin who needs to be introduced to sex and so to be initiated into life. This makes Marian realize her self and here she decides to escape from Peter. Her involvement with Duncan forces her to refuse to eat, and she takes a successful flight away from Peter and his party. Atwood's Marian realizes that she has been used as an edible item by Peter, whereas Duncan allows her to think freely and act. Peter encroaches into Marian's mind which reveals his attitude of consumerism. In the name of marriage Atwood's Marian is trapped. The institution of marriage mostly treats women as a saleable commodity and sex object, in brief, a consumer product to be used up and thrown out.

To Peter Marian is an edible item. The first time, on a Valentine's Day Marian prepares a cake in the shape of a heart and offers it to Peter. She wants him to take it. Marian identifies her with the heart that is happily tasted by Peter. For the second time, she prepares another cake in the shape of a woman and offers it to Peter. As Peter sees the image of Marian in the cake, he refuses to take it and leaves the place. But when the same cake is offered to Duncan who is able to understand the difference between an 'image' and an 'identity', he accepts it. Marian also eats the cake because it is just a cake.

After leaving Peer, Marian takes Duncan as a confidant and a true friend. She takes his voice and suggestion as an oracle. But Duncan does not take her views seriously. While she decides to meet a psychiatrist for her problems Duncan prevents her from doing so. He gives an evasive answer: "Don't ask me, that's your problem. It does take as though you ought to do something; self-laceration in a vacuum eventually gets rather boring. But it's your own personal cul-de-sac, you invented it, you'll have to think of your own way out" (264). Marian gains her strength to reassemble her lost self. At the beginning when she was ignored by Peter at the party with Len she madly ran on the road. This flight seems ridiculous and stupid to her now. She is ready to face Peter with a clear vision. She invites him to her room where she offers him a cake in the shape of a woman. While offering the cake she says, "You've been trying to destroy me, haven't you.... You've been trying to assimilate me. But I've made you a substitute, something you'll like much better. This is what you really wanted all along, isn't it?" (271). Marian, remains single in order to escape from marriage and to retain her 'self' intact. Their problems come to an unresolved stand-still as they have to go back to their family. Their search for identity continues, even as their problems persist.

Atwood's *The Edible Woman* novel takes up for study address the issue of the protagonist desire to get her self free from the clutches of the male oriented social norms. Marian McAlpin, the protagonist releases herself from the bondage of marriage when she comes to know that Peter wants to marry her only to keep her as a good cook. Marian wants to escape from the society that treats woman as an edible item. She hates Peter for his male chauvinistic attitude and promotes her liking towards Duncan, and thus she facilitates her individuality; subsequently she remains single and keeps her self intact. In this novel Marian, protagonist liberates herself from the women related problems and begin to subscribe to a style of living where she is ample space for individual's desires and ultimately, for absolute freedom. However, one should remember that the protagonist willingly position herself within the framework of her east and west society.

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